

Table 1: Summary of Queries Used in Databases.

The table outlines the queries used in each database during the study, including the results obtained.

Database	Search query	Results
Search Strategy 1: Learning Analytics AND Machine Learning		
The ACM Digital Library	(Title:"learning analytics" OR Title:LA OR Title:"educational data mining" OR Title:"data-driven education" OR Title:"Social Learning Analytics" OR Title:SLA OR Abstract:"learning analytics" OR Abstract:LA OR Abstract:"educational data mining" OR Abstract:"data-driven education" OR Abstract:"Social Learning Analytics" OR Abstract:SLA OR Keyword:"learning analytics" OR Keyword:LA OR Keyword:"educational data mining" OR Keyword:"data-driven education" OR Keyword:"Social Learning Analytics" OR Keyword:SLA) AND (Title:"Machine Learning" OR Title:ML OR Abstract:"Machine Learning" OR Abstract:ML OR Keyword:"Machine Learning" OR Keyword:ML) AND (Title:"higher education" OR Title:universit* OR Abstract:"higher education" OR Abstract:universit* OR Keyword:"higher education" OR Keyword:universit*)	32, filtered: 1
IEEE Xplore	("Document Title":"learning analytics" OR "Document Title":LA OR "Document Title":"educational data mining" OR "Document Title":"data-driven education" OR "Document Title":"Social Learning Analytics" OR "Document Title":SLA OR "Abstract":"learning analytics" OR "Abstract":LA OR "Abstract":"educational data mining" OR "Abstract":"data-driven education" OR "Abstract":"Social Learning Analytics" OR "Abstract":SLA OR "Index Terms":"learning analytics" OR "Index Terms":LA OR "Index Terms":"educational data mining" OR "Index Terms":"data-driven education" OR "Index Terms":"Social Learning Analytics" OR "Index Terms":SLA) AND ("Document Title":"Machine Learning" OR "Document Title":ML OR "Abstract":"Machine Learning" OR "Abstract":ML OR "Index Terms":"Machine Learning" OR "Index Terms":ML) AND ("Document Title":"higher education" OR "Document Title":universit* OR "Abstract":"higher education" OR "Abstract":universit* OR "Index Terms":"higher education" OR "Index Terms":universit*)	117, filtered 7
Emerald	(title:"learning analytics" OR title:LA OR title:"educational data mining" OR title:"data-driven education" OR title:"Social Learning Analytics" OR title:SLA OR abstract:"learning analytics" OR abstract:LA OR abstract:"educational data mining" OR abstract:"data-driven education" OR abstract:"Social Learning Analytics" OR abstract:SLA OR keyword:"learning analytics" OR keyword:LA OR keyword:"educational data mining" OR keyword:"data-driven education" OR keyword:"Social Learning Analytics" OR keyword:SLA) AND (title:"Machine Learning" OR title:ML OR abstract:"Machine Learning" OR abstract:ML OR keyword:"Machine Learning" OR keyword:ML) AND (title:"higher education" OR title:universit* OR abstract:"higher education" OR abstract:universit* OR keyword:"higher education" OR keyword:universit*)	5, filtered 5
ERIC	(TI "learning analytics" OR TI "LA" OR TI "educational data mining" OR TI "data-driven education" OR TI "Social Learning Analytics" OR TI "SLA" OR AB "learning analytics" OR AB "LA" OR AB "educational data mining" OR AB "data-driven education" OR AB "Social Learning Analytics" OR AB "SLA" OR KW "learning analytics" OR KW "LA" OR KW "educational data mining" OR KW "data-driven education" OR KW "Social Learning Analytics" OR KW "SLA") AND (TI "Machine Learning" OR TI "ML" OR AB "Machine Learning" OR AB "ML" OR KW "Machine Learning" OR KW "ML") AND (TI "higher education" OR TI universit* OR AB "higher education" OR AB universit* OR KW "higher education" OR KW universit*)	21, post-filter 17

ProQuest	(ti("learning analytics") OR ti(LA) OR ti("educational data mining") OR ti("data-driven education") OR ti("Social Learning Analytics") OR ti(SLA) OR ab("learning analytics") OR ab(LA) OR ab("educational data mining") OR ab("data-driven education") OR ab("Social Learning Analytics") OR ab(SLA) OR mainsubject("learning analytics") OR mainsubject(LA) OR mainsubject("educational data mining") OR mainsubject("data-driven education") OR mainsubject("Social Learning Analytics") OR mainsubject(SLA)) AND (ti("Machine Learning") OR ti("ML") OR ab("Machine Learning") OR ab("ML") OR mainsubject("Machine Learning") OR mainsubject("ML")) AND (ti("higher education") OR ti(universit*) OR ab("higher education") OR ab(universit*) OR mainsubject("higher education") OR mainsubject(universit*))	434, post-filter 212
Sage Journals	<i>(Title:"learning analytics" OR Title:"LA" OR Title:"educational data mining" OR Title:"data-driven education" OR Title:"Social Learning Analytics" OR Title:"SLA" OR Abstract:"learning analytics" OR Abstract:"LA" OR Abstract:"educational data mining" OR Abstract:"data-driven education" OR Abstract:"Social Learning Analytics" OR Abstract:"SLA" OR Keyword:"learning analytics" OR Keyword:"LA" OR Keyword:"educational data mining" OR Keyword:"data-driven education" OR Keyword:"Social Learning Analytics" OR Keyword:"SLA") AND (Title:"Machine Learning" OR Title:"ML" OR Abstract:"Machine Learning" OR Abstract:"ML" OR Keyword:"Machine Learning" OR Keyword:"ML") AND (Title:"higher education" OR Title:"universit*" OR Abstract:"higher education" OR Abstract:"universit*" OR Keyword:"higher education" OR Keyword:"universit*")</i>	3, post-filter 3
Web of Science	(TI=("learning analytics") OR TI=(LA) OR TI=("educational data mining") OR TI=("data-driven education") OR TI=("Social Learning Analytics") OR TI=(SLA) OR AB=("learning analytics") OR AB=(LA) OR AB=("educational data mining") OR AB=("data-driven education") OR AB=("Social Learning Analytics") OR AB=(SLA) OR TS=("learning analytics") OR TS=(LA) OR TS=("educational data mining") OR TS=("data-driven education") OR TS=("Social Learning Analytics") OR TS=(SLA)) AND (TI=("Machine Learning") OR TI=("ML") OR AB=("Machine Learning") OR AB=(ML) OR TS=("Machine Learning") OR TS=(ML)) AND (TI=("higher education") OR TI=(universit*) OR AB=("higher education") OR AB=(universit*) OR TS=("higher education") OR TS=(universit*))	400, post-filter 291
ScienceDirect	<i>Title, abstract or author-specified keywords: ("learning analytics" OR LA OR "educational data mining" OR "data-driven education" OR "Social Learning Analytics") AND ("Machine Learning" OR "ML") AND ("higher education" OR university)</i>	277, post-filter 221
Wiley Online Library	<i>("learning analytics" OR LA OR "educational data mining" OR "data-driven education" OR "Social Learning Analytics" OR SLA) AND ("Machine Learning" OR "ML") AND ("higher education" OR universit*)</i>	6941, post-filter 344
Taylor and Francis	<i>("learning analytics" OR LA OR "educational data mining" OR "data-driven education" OR "Social Learning Analytics") AND ("Machine Learning" OR "ML") AND ("higher education" OR university)</i>	361, post-filter 361
Scopus	("learning analytics" OR "educational data mining" OR "data-driven education" OR "Social Learning Analytics" OR "SLA") AND ("Machine Learning" OR "ML") AND ("higher education" OR universit*)	416 post-filter 174

Search Strategy 2: Learning Analytics AND Generative Artificial Intelligence

The ACM Digital Library	(Title:"learning analytics" OR Title:LA OR Title:"educational data mining" OR Title:"data-driven education" OR Title:"Social Learning Analytics" OR Title:SLA OR Abstract:"learning analytics" OR Abstract:LA OR Abstract:"educational data mining" OR Abstract:"data-driven education" OR Abstract:"Social Learning Analytics" OR Abstract:SLA OR Keyword:"learning analytics" OR Keyword:LA OR Keyword:"educational data mining" OR Keyword:"data-driven education" OR Keyword:"Social Learning Analytics" OR Keyword:SLA) AND (Title:"Machine Learning" OR Title:ML OR Abstract:"Machine Learning" OR Abstract:ML OR Keyword:"Machine Learning" OR Keyword:ML) AND (Title:"higher education" OR Title:universit* OR Abstract:"higher education" OR Abstract:universit* OR Keyword:"higher education" OR Keyword:universit*)	52 post-filter 52
IEEE Xplore	(Title: "learning analytics" OR Title: LA OR Title: "educational data mining" OR Title: "data-driven education" OR Title: "Social Learning Analytics" OR Title: SLA OR Abstract: "learning analytics" OR Abstract: LA OR Abstract: "educational data mining" OR Abstract: "data-driven education" OR Abstract: "Social Learning Analytics" OR Abstract: SLA OR Keyword: "learning analytics" OR Keyword: LA OR Keyword: "educational data mining" OR Keyword: "data-driven education" OR Keyword: "Social Learning Analytics" OR Keyword: SLA) AND (Title: "Generative Artificial Intelligence" OR Title: "Generative AI" OR Title: "GenAI" OR Title: "Large Language Model" OR Title: "LLM" OR Title: "GPT" OR Abstract: "Generative Artificial Intelligence" OR Abstract: "Generative AI" OR Abstract: "GenAI" OR Abstract: "Large Language Model" OR Abstract: "LLM" OR Abstract: "GPT" OR Keyword: "Generative Artificial Intelligence" OR Keyword: "Generative AI" OR Keyword: "GenAI" OR Keyword: "Large Language Model" OR Keyword: "LLM" OR Keyword: "GPT")	7 post-filter 7
Springer Nature Link (EC-TEL)	("learning analytics" OR "LA" OR "educational data mining" OR "data-driven education" OR "Social Learning Analytics" OR "SLA") AND ("Machine Learning" OR "ML") AND ("higher education" OR universit*)	6 post-filter 6
Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("learning analytics") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("LA") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("educational data mining") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("data-driven education") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Social Learning Analytics") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("SLA")) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Generative Artificial Intelligence") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Generative AI") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("GenAI") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Large Language Model") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("LLM") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("GPT")) AND PUBYEAR > 2019 AND PUBYEAR < 2026	518 post-filter 373